

RELATION BETWEEN THE LATTICE ENERGY, MELTING POINT
AND BOILING POINT OF SOME CRYSTALLINE SUBSTANCES.
PART I. THE ALKALI HALIDES

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It is found that the expressions lattice energy (U_0)/melting point (T_m) and (U_0)/boiling point (T_b) are approximately constant for the alkali halides. Slightly higher values for the halides of Li appear to be due to the presence of covalency.

It appears that the potential energy (U_g) of the gaseous state bears an approximate constant ratio to the respective U_0 in these systems. Making use of this relationship it has been shown that U_0/T_b should be approximately constant.

Trouton's rule (*Phil. Mag.*, 1884, 18, 54) and its later improvements by Nernst (*Nachrichten*, 1906), Bingham (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28, 723), Forcrand (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, 156, 1439, 1648, 1809), Hildebrand (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 37, 970; 1918, 40, 45; *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 233) and Halford (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, 8, 496) describe the behaviour of liquids during evaporation. Similar empirical and semi-empirical attempts to study the behaviour of solids at the melting point have been made by Walden (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1908, 14, 713), Kordes (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 160, 67) and others. Rigorous mathematical procedures have been adopted by Eyring (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1937, 5, 396), Lennard-Jones and Devonshire (*Proc. Roy Soc.*, 1939, 169A, 317; 1939, 170A, 464) and Rice (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 136, 883; 1941, 9, 121; 1944, 12, 1) to study the liquid systems. It appears, however, that these authors have mostly confined themselves either to substances which are liquids at ordinary temperatures or to liquid metals. Substances which melt at higher temperatures to give liquids containing ions appear to have received only very scanty attention.

As the solid is gradually heated from the absolute zero upwards through the melting point into the liquid state, and then finally at the boiling point into vapour, the substance goes on absorbing heat energy which operates against the binding forces of the constituents of the lattice in the crystal, and thus the potential energy (i. e. the lattice energy, U_0) of the lattice constituents is reduced with a corresponding increase in their kinetic energy. As the properties of a crystal, such as the lattice energy, the m. p. and the b. p. represent directly or indirectly the magnitude of the ionic forces, and hence its stability (cf. Stillwell, "Crystal Chemistry", 1938, p. 213 ff.), one might expect to discover a possible relationship between the lattice energy, m. p.* and b. p. of the crystalline substances. The present communication is an outcome of such an attempt.

Relationship between the unit-cell dimensions of crystals and their melting points in the case of halogenobenzenes and methylbenzenes has been investigated by T. Beacall (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1943, 39, 214; 1945, 41, 472).

The data regarding lattice energy (U_0), m. p. (T_m) and the b. p. (T_b) have been obtained from the Landolt-Börnstein Tables, International Critical Tables, Handbook of Physics and Chemistry (1944), "Electronic Structure and Chemical Binding" (1940) by O. K. Rice, and "Introduction to Physical Chemistry" (1940) by Moelwyn Hughes : these have been utilised for the calculation of various quantities considered in this communication.

TABLE I

Substance.	U_0 (k cal./mole).	T_m .	T_b	U_0/T_m .	U_0/T_b .
LiF	240.1	1143	1943	0.2115	0.1236
LiCl	199.2	886	1656	0.2249, 0.12030	0.1203
LiBr	188.2	820	1538	0.2296	0.1224
LiI	174.2	719	1463	0.2423	0.1190
NaF	213.4	1253	1973	0.1703	0.1081
NaCl	183.1	1077	1686	0.1700	0.1086
NaBr	174.6	1028	1663	0.1700	0.1051
NaI	163.9	924	1573	0.1774	0.1042
KF	189.7	1153	1773	0.1645	0.1070
KCl	165.4	1048	1689	0.1585	0.0979
KBr	159.3	1003	1653	0.1588	0.0943
KI	150.8	996	1603	0.1515	0.0941
RbF	181.6	1033	1683	0.1758	0.1079
RbCl	160.1	988	1663	0.1620	0.0962
RbBr	153.5	957	1613	0.1604	0.0952
RbI	145.3	913	1573	0.1592	0.0924
CsF	173.7	956	1523	0.1817	0.1140
CsCl	152.2	919	1563	0.1656	0.0974
CsBr	146.3	909	1573	0.1610	0.0931
CsI	139.1	894	1553	0.1556	0.0896

The values of the lattice energy U_0 for different substances obtained from the Born-Haber Cycle experimentally and those calculated theoretically agree closely (cf. Moelwyn-Hughes, *loc. cit.*). T_m is given in degree absolute.

Lattice Energy and Melting Point

It appears that except for the lithium salts the values of U_0/T_m are very nearly constant for the different halides of Na, K, Rb and Cs, the extreme values being 0.1515 (KI) and 0.1817 (CsF), the average being 0.1615. It appears most probable that the substances which fuse to give liquids containing constituents in a similar state of mutual interaction, give nearly equal values for U_0/T_m . In lithium halides, where covalency is appreciable (cf. Evans, "Crystal Chemistry", pp. 180-82); the values

of U_0/T_m are higher. Due to the presence of covalency, there is no uniform distribution of attractive forces, and thus loosening of some parts occurs as compared to others. This causes the substance to melt at a lower temperature than would be the case if a uniform distribution of the lattice forces were present.

Lattice Energy and the Boiling Point

The conclusions arrived at from the study of the ratio U_0/T_m are also supported by the study of the ratio U_0/T_b . The boiling point T_b and the values of U_0/T_b are given in Table I. Here again, except for slightly higher values of U_0/T_b for lithium halides, the values for the halides of other alkali metals are very nearly constant, the extreme values being 0.08958(CsI) and 0.1140(CsF) and average being 0.1020. The higher values of U_0/T_b for lithium halides are perhaps due to covalency, as explained previously.

The study of the ratio U_0/T_b becomes all the more interesting if we take into consideration the potential energy of the gaseous state (U_g) and as will be clear from Table II, it appears to be an approximate constant fraction of the respective U_0 i. e. U_0/U_g is approximately constant for similar substances. This is clear from Table II.

TABLE II

(The values of U_0 have been taken from Table I)

Substance.	U_g (kcal./mole).*	U_0/U_g .	Substance.	U_g (kcal./mole).*	U_0/U_g .
LiF	192	1.240	KF	134	1.403
LiCl	140	1.393	KCl	111	1.469
LiBr	130	1.423	KBr	106	1.481
LiI	117	1.462	KI	99	1.505
NaF	160	1.331	RbF	125	1.440
NaCl	126	1.396	RbCl	106	1.490
NaBr	119	1.445	RbBr	101	1.490
NaI	108	1.448	RbI	95	1.505

See Moelwyn-Hughes, *loc. cit.*

The consequences of this relationship must be far reaching. It implies that boiling in similar substances (i. e. those in which U_0 is similarly distributed in the lattice) appears to occur at such a temperature at which U_g bears approximately the same ratio to U_0 of the substance in question. This will result in an approximate constancy of U_0/T_b . This can be shown as follows :

$$U_0/U_g = \frac{U_0 - I_1 - I_2 - H}{U_0} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or a constant } C = 1 - \frac{I_1}{U_0} - \frac{I_2}{U_0} - \frac{H}{U_0} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where H - heat absorbed in raising T from $0^\circ K$ to T_b ; L - latent heat of fusion; L_e - latent heat of evaporation.

It can be reasonably assumed* that L_f and L_e , under similar conditions, would be roughly proportional to U_0 in similar substances. Hence (1) gives

$$C - K - \frac{H}{U_0} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Again roughly $C_p T_b \approx C_v T_b \approx 3nRT_b \approx 6nT_b$, where n is the number of atoms in the molecule.

Hence (2) gives

$$K - C \approx 6nT_b/U_0 - B$$

or $U_0/T_b \approx \frac{6n}{K - C} \approx \frac{6n}{B} - K_1$

Similarly U_0/T_m can be shown to be approximately constant for similar substances.

Thus, one is led to conclude that :

(i) Substances in which the lattice energy is similarly distributed among the various constituents of the lattice, give approximately a constant value for U_0/T_m and U_0/T_b . In such cases it appears from available evidence that the potential energy of the gaseous state bears an approximate constant ratio to the lattice energy of the crystal.

(ii) If a part of the lattice energy is bound in covalency, e. g. in lithium halides, the ratios U_0/T_m and U_0/T_b have higher values than those for purely electrovalent systems. In such cases the values of T_m and T_b would be, in general, comparatively low.

(iii) The boiling points and, to a lesser extent, the melting points for similar substances may be considered as the corresponding temperatures even for alkali halides which are, at ordinary temperatures, crystalline solids.

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* It is almost impossible to support this assumption by experimental evidence as the values of L_f and L_e are not known in many cases. However, as both L_f and L_e would be small as compared to U_0 , L_f/U_0 and L_e/U_0 will be negligible as compared to unity.